

Entrepreneurial Education and Professional Exclusivity of Nigerian University Students in Cross River State

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Abstract:- This paper explores the impact of entrepreneurship education on professional advancement among 500 students drawn from Arthur Jarvis University, Cross River State University and University of Calabar. The study adopted survey research design. Two research questions and hypotheses were raised for the study. Data were collected using structured questionnaire. Findings showed that exposure to entrepreneurship education influences professional exclusivity.

Keywords:- Entrepreneurship Education, Professional, Exclusivity.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the hovering unemployment rate in Nigeria, self employment and small organization projects are currently high at the country's country wide agenda, within side the wish that they'll offer opportunity channels of employment. Yearly, thousand of college graduates form part of the labour marketplace looking for gainful employment. The venture is as a result one of now no longer simplest tackling the already significant unemployed graduates, however additionally of soaking up the brand new entrants into the labour marketplace. Underlying this example is the reality that the education which university students acquire has now no longer been fully a hit in equipping them with ideal talents and capabilities required for activity advent and self employment (Amaewhule, 2007). The consciousness of this essential reality underlies the directive of the Federal Government to all tertiary schooling regulatory groups to set up vital mechanisms for the introduction, improvement and sustenance of entrepreneurial lifestyle amongst Nigerian youths. To make up for the curricula inadequacies in assembly employment problem, the National Universities Commission (NUC) in July, 2004, prepared a

workshop on entrepreneurship for Nigerian universities as a manner forward. The NUC workshop produced a draft curriculum on entrepreneurial research for Nigerian Universities. Consequently, many Universities have initiated entrepreneurship schooling programmes in a try and opposite graduate unemployment fashion via means of giving the wanted education in entrepreneurship to college students for putting in place organizations and to recall self employment as a possible profession option. Entrepreneurship education in step with Isaac, Visser, Friedrich and Brijlal (2007) is the functional intervention via means of an educator within side the lifestyles of the learner to continue to exist within side the global of commercial enterprise. It has as its recognition a motion orientation broadly speaking embodied in coaching college students the way to increase a commercial enterprise plan (Ronstadt, 1985). Entrepreneurship education develops and stimulates entrepreneurial process, offering all gear vital for taking off new ventures (Postigo and Tomborini 2002). It is typically believed that entrepreneurship schooling is an vital that would make a tremendous contribution to enhancing the entrepreneurship orientation of people, main to the purchase of talents, creativity, confidence, power and courage, to be able to create employment for self and others. Entrepreneurship schooling has come to indicate all styles of information shipping that are looking for to empower the individual to create actual wealth withinside the financial sector, thereby advancing the reason of improvement of the country as a whole. According to Bassey and Archibong (2005), the intention of entrepreneurship schooling is supposed to empower our graduates no matter their regions of specialization with talents so as to allow them to interact in earnings yielding venture, if they may be not able to steady jobs withinside the public sector. It is a reorientation from activity seekers to activity creators.

The purpose for the inclusion of entrepreneurship curricula in universities in keeping with Cotton, O'Gorman and Stampfi (2000) is that it's going to assist graduates to accumulate multiplied know-how of entrepreneurship, equip them with entrepreneurial method to the arena of labor and put together them to behave as marketers and executives of new businesses. Thus, the targets of entrepreneurship schooling as succinctly provided with the aid of using the European Union (2002) include: "elevating college students' focus of self employment as a profession option (the message being that you may become now no longer handiest an employee, however additionally an employer); selling the improvement of private traits which are applicable to entrepreneurship, which includes creativity, threat taking and responsibility; and imparting the technical and enterprise skills which are wanted with the intention to begin a brand new venture". From the foregoing it could be deduced that publicity of university college students to entrepreneurial schooling will ginger- up entrepreneurial power in college students and if nicely packaged, can be a good sized aspect in continual unemployment discount amongst graduates. In Nigeria, entrepreneurship schooling remains at its infancy. While maximum Nigerian universities have initiated the programme, little studies is to be had to evaluate its effect and additionally to affirm if a dating exists between college students taking guides in entrepreneurship and their goal of turning into marketers. In this context, it's miles of number one significance to apprehend whether or not entrepreneurship schooling increases profession intentions to be entrepreneur typically or whether or not it enables college students decide how properly acceptable they're for entrepreneurship. This look at therefore explores the effect of entrepreneurship schooling on profession goal of tertiary schooling college students.

A. Statement of the Problem

It has been found out formerly that the form of training provided in maximum tertiary establishments produce graduates for whom there may be no marketplace demands. Graduates are produced for salary employment within side the formal sector. Unemployment of graduates from Nigerian tertiary organization has grow to be a prime countrywide problem. The duration among commencement and employment dates has persisted to prolong and this has grow to be a supply of frustration for graduates. In the circumstance, it's far apparent that the best possible alternative is self employment. Currently maximum universities have initiated entrepreneurship training programmes within side the wish that it's going to equip college graduates with abilities essential to begin their very own businesses, to be activity creators, rather than activity seekers. This is sequel to the directives with the aid of using Federal Government of Nigeria to all tertiary establishments, to provide entrepreneurship training courses if you want to beautify the abilities acquisition of tertiary training graduates for self employment. This paper therefore tries to discover the effect of entrepreneurship training on profession intentions of tertiary training students.

B. Research questions

Two research questions guided the study as follows:

- What are the career intentions of tertiary education students?
- What level of skills do students acquire after completing an entrepreneurship course?

C. Hypotheses

Two hypotheses were formulated to direct the study

- The benefits of entrepreneurship education is not significantly high.
- Students perceived barriers to starting a business venture is not significantly high.

II. LITERATURE

Previous studies research have proven that there's a extensive dating among entrepreneurship schooling and profession aim. For example, a look at via way of means of Kolvereid and Moen (1997) has proven that scholars with a first-rate in entrepreneurship have a better aim to interact as marketers and are probably to provoke commercial enterprise. Another look at via way of means of Noel (2001) showed that scholars who graduated in entrepreneurship reached better rankings in entrepreneurial aim and entrepreneurial self-efficacy than college students who graduated in different disciplines. Similarly, Varela and Jimenez (2001) look at has proven that there's a correlation among a university's funding withinside the promoting of entrepreneurship and the proportion of college students turning into marketers. Additional studies via way of means of Autio, Keeley, Klofsten and Ulfstedt (1997) observed that entrepreneurship schooling creates a fine picture for the marketers and contributes to the selection of entrepreneurship as a expert opportunity via way of means of graduates. Wilson, Kickul and Marlino (2007) observed that, entrepreneurship schooling may also boom pupil's hobby in entrepreneurship as a profession. Weihe and Reich (1993) performed an global look at of entrepreneurial hobby amongst commercial enterprise pupil and observed that 34.3% of these interviewed had an unreserved hobby in self-employment. The look at observed the highest wide variety of college students already self-employed, 6%, turned into in America. Similarly, Tkachev and Kolvereid (1999) findings confirmed that the self employment intentions amongst college students may be extended via Entrepreneurship Training Programme (ETP). Scott and Twomey (1988), of their look at, accrued facts from English college students and suggested that 25 percentage had a commercial enterprise concept and forty one percentage aspired to self employment. A studies that turned into performed to a pattern of one thousand MBA college students from pinnacle commercial enterprise faculties in USA confirmed that 44% spoke back that they desired to become " an impartial entrepreneur", whilst 34% wanted to be "a high-ranking company manager" (Sandholtz, 1990). Also, Owusu-Ansah (2004) studied the effect of entrepreneurship schooling on profession intentions and aspirations of tertiary college students in Ghana and observed that an awesome 77.9%

of the survey respondents indicated they had been stimulated to a huge or a totally huge volume to provoke commercial enterprise start-ups. Indication turned into additionally that 86.7% of the survey respondents felt equip with competencies and talents to provoke and run their very own businesses.

Bassey and Olu (2008) investigated how college students` belief of tertiary entrepreneurship schooling relate to graduate self employment capacity in Nigeria the usage of a pattern of 690 college students in 3 universities. The findings confirmed that there has been a full-size courting among college students` belief of University administration's provision for tertiary entrepreneurship schooling, curriculum goals for tertiary entrepreneurship schooling, academic strategies for tertiary entrepreneurship schooling, nice and amount of tertiary entrepreneurship schooling teachers and college students` entrepreneurial trends and graduate self-employment capacity. The purpose of this gift examine is to cognizance at the effect of entrepreneurship schooling on profession intentions of tertiary schooling college students.

III. METHODS

It has been found out formerly that the form of training provided in maximum tertiary establishments produce graduates for whom there may be no marketplace demands. Graduates are produced for salary employment withinside the formal sector. Unemployment of graduates from Nigerian tertiary organization has grow to be a prime countrywide problem. The duration among commencement and employment dates has persisted to prolong and this has grow to be a supply of frustration for graduates. In the circumstance, it's far apparent that the best possible alternative is self employment. Currently maximum universities have initiated entrepreneurship training programmes withinside the wish that it's going to equip college graduates with abilities essential to begin their very own businesses, to be activity creators, rather than activity seekers. This is sequel to the directives with the aid of using Federal Government of Nigeria to all tertiary establishments, to provide entrepreneurship training courses if you want to beautify the abilities acquisition of tertiary training graduates for self employment. This paper therefore tries to discover the effect of entrepreneurship training on profession intentions of tertiary training students.

IV. RESULT

A. Research question 1

What are the profession intentions of tertiary schooling students? The respondents have been requested to suggest their profession intentions after graduation. Results discovered that majority of the respondents 29.6% (148) indicated employment, 26.8% (134) indicated self employment, 21% (105) employment and element time commercial enterprise, 15% (75) similarly research, similarly research and element time commercial enterprise 7.6% (38).Table 1 outlines the profession intentions of students. Quite revealing from this

locating is the reality that 29.6% of the survey respondents indicated employment while 26.8% indicated self employment. Apparently 21% desired joint profession intentions. This end result may be given several interpretations. In the primary place, it seems that maximum undergraduates nonetheless opt to be withinside the employment of others Which is a sign of excessive choice for remunerative job. This corroborates the sooner findings of Onuma (2009) that maximum Nigerian graduates aimed for salary employment withinside the formal sector. Their social expectancies are orientated to operating and having a profession withinside the control of personal organisations or for a profession withinside the public sector. Also (Ussman and Postigo, 2000) in Postigo and Tamborini (2002), stated that, the instructional programmes of maximum universities will be inclined to consciousness the training in their college students in the direction of a expert profession as employees and seldom recall the possibility of growing competences a good way to permit alumni to begin their very own projects. The truth that 26% had goal of beginning their commercial enterprise is a sign that entrepreneurship training has created a high quality effect at the respondent to recall self employment as a profession option. This locating affirms Autio et al (1997) studies that entrepreneurship training created a high quality photograph for entrepreneurship as a profession. It additionally corroborates Fayolle (2005) view that entrepreneurship publications create greater entrepreneurship college students which in turn lead in the end to a more variety of college students inclined to begin their very own agencies. This locating additionally concurs with that of Kolvereid and Moen (1997) that graduates with entrepreneurship main have been much more likely to begin new agencies and had more potent entrepreneurial goal than different graduates. A main revealing locating of this have a look at is the choice of the respondents to have a joint profession goal of coming into into employment and strolling a commercial enterprise on component-time basis. This locating indicates the reluctance of the respondents to take hazard. A doable clarification is the plain method of producing budget to finance the component time commercial enterprise. This articulation is in consonance with Owusa-Ansa (2004), who stated that combining employment and component-time commercial enterprise is a hazard diversification method of producing capital to finance the commercial enterprise start-up. Finance is a main barrier to commercial enterprise start - up in Nigeria. A joint profession goal could in all likelihood offer the important price range for commercial enterprise start- up and could function a back- up.

B. Research question 2

The end result of this have a look at upholds the preceding findings of Thandi and Sharma (2004) that, entrepreneurship courses can certainly boost the extent of college students` abilities on entrepreneurial activity. Equally, those findings help the arguments of Garavan and O`Cinnede (1994) that, schooling or education can have an impact on the improvement of entrepreneurial role. Evidently, the end result of this have a look at is a sign that entrepreneurship schooling has, to a positive extent, created a wonderful effect at the respondents

and has raised their stage of abilities. This locating is instructive in opposition to the history that entrepreneurship education in Cross River universities is incredibly latest and simply taught for a semester on an advert hoc basis. Besides, maximum of the academics who educate the route aren't experts. Moderate talent is likewise a demonstration that an awful lot of what's performed is theoretical with little or no publicity to realistic aspect. This should but be because of loss of facilities.

C. Hypothesis 1

The benefit of entrepreneurship education to student is not significantly high. This hypothesis is a one variable hypothesis. The test statistic used in analyzing data relevant to it was population t-test for one sampled study. In carrying out the test the researchers first determined the population mean (μ) using the 4 point scale. The scale spanned from strongly agree (4points) to strongly disagree (1point). Thereafter, all the points on the scale were added up. The results were then aggregated for the ten items measuring the variable to give 25.0 ($2.5 \times 10 = 25.0$). With this, the sample mean ($\bar{x}$) was compared with the population mean (μ) to obtain the t-value.

The results are presented in Table 3.

The results in Table 3 indicate that the calculated t-value of 30.314 is greater than the critical t-value of 1.65 at 0.05 level of significance with 499 degrees of freedom. This means that the benefit of entrepreneurship education to students is significantly high. By this result the null hypothesis is rejected.

This findings corroborates the previous research findings of Kolvereid and Moen (1997), Owusu-Ansah (2004) and Cotton et al (2000) that entrepreneurship education helps graduates to acquire increased understanding of entrepreneurship and equip them with skills relevant for job creation. A deduction from these findings is that the benefits of entrepreneurship education are significantly high. The study evidence shows that entrepreneurship education creates inspiring awareness to business opportunity, provides exposure to entrepreneurship process, builds self confidence, equip students with knowledge and skills and engender self employment as a career option.

D. Hypothesis 2

Students` perceived obstacles to beginning a commercial enterprise challenge isn't always drastically high. The take a look at statistic utilized in reading information applicable to this speculation turned into populace t-take a look at for one pattern mean.

The outcomes of the evaluation are offered in Table four. Results in Table four indicates that the calculated t-price of 6.443 is extra than the crucial t-price of 1.sixty five at 0.05 level of importance with 499 tiers of freedom. This method that college students' perceived obstacles to commercial enterprise begin up is drastically high. The null speculation is rejected. From the findings, it's miles apparent that some of limitations do but militate in opposition to beginning a commercial enterprise challenge. High amongst those being loss of get right of entry to to beginning capital and absence of commercial enterprise ideas. This locating upholds the studies formerly mentioned with the aid of using Owusu-Ansah (2004) that many college students and graduates understand numerous limitations that exceptionally have an effect on the results of entrepreneurship programmes. Among the perceived elements encompass gaining get right of entry to to finance, loss of commercial enterprise control skills, loss of revel in and ideas. In addition there's the added burden of loss of a credit score records that thwart efforts at getting credit score from the banking system.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings of this examine display that entrepreneurship training influences definitely at the profession intentions of tertiary training college students. As it's far proven on this examine, entrepreneurship training ends in boom within side the degree of college students understanding in entrepreneurial process. The gift initiative through the National University Commission (NUC) in integrating entrepreneurship training into the formal University curriculum is making enormous contribution in encouraging a effective orientation amongst University undergraduates. It is was hoping that this initiative will bridge the hole and alternate the attitude of tertiary training graduates from process seekers to process creators.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based at the findings of this study, the subsequent hints are made:

- The length and depth of the entrepreneurship schooling must be expanded past a semester`s route to realise a most effect on college students.
- Entrepreneurship schooling must now no longer best be presented on the college stage however must be entrenched and made obligatory in any respect different degrees of schooling.
- Access to finance via way of means of micro, small and medium establishments have to be properly liberalized via way of means of the government. There must be unhindered get entry to to micro-credit score for younger graduates.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Amaewhule, W. A. (2007). *Education, the world of work and the challenge of change: In search of intervention strategies*. Inaugural lecture series No. 23; River State University of Science and Technology, Nkpolu Port Harcourt.
- [2]. Autio, E., Keeley, R, Klofsten, M. & Ulfstedt, T. (1997). Entrepreneurial Intent among Students: Testing an intent model in Asia, Scandinavia and in USA. *Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research*, Babson conference proceeding.
- [3]. Bassey, U. U. & Archibong, I. A. (2005). Assuring quality graduate output through entrepreneurial oriented education in Nigerian universities. *Nigerian Journal of Curriculum Studies*, 12(3),18-23.
- [4]. Bassey, U. U. & Olu D. (2008). Tertiary Education and Graduate Self-Employment Potentials in Nigeria. *Journal of the World Universities Forum*, 1(3), 131 - 42.
- [5]. Cotton, J., O'Gorman, C. & Stampfi, C. (2002). *Can national education policies meet the call for more entrepreneur?* A project supported by the European community (Project Number - FIN/00/C/P/RF/92650) (www.google.com); March, 2005.
- [6]. European Union. (2002). Final report of the expert group "Best procedure" project on Education and Training for Entrepreneurship. Brussels: European Commission Directorate - General for Enterprise.
- [7]. Fayolle, A. (2005). Evaluation of Entrepreneurship Education: behaviour performing or intention increasing. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business*, 1(2) 1, 89 - 98.
- [8]. Garavan, T. N. & O'Conneide, B. (1994). Entrepreneurship education and training programmes: a review and evaluation, *Journal of European Training*, 18(8), 3 - 12. education and training (FET) level in South Africa. *South African Journal of Education*, 27, 613 - 629.
- [9]. Kolvereid, L. & Moen, O. (1997). Entrepreneurship among business graduates: Does a major in entrepreneurship make a difference? *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 21 (4), 154.
- [10]. Madumere-Obike, C. U. (2000). Reposition Education for Employment: Implications for educational management. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Research Development (MIKJORED)*; 7(3) 43-52.
- [11]. Noel, T.W. (2001). *Effects of entrepreneurial education on student to open a business*. Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research, Babson, Conference Proceedings. Babson College.
- [12]. Nwangwu I. O. (2007). Entrepreneurship in education. Concept and constraints. *African Journal of Education and Developmental Studies* 4(1), 196 - 207.
- [13]. Onuma, N. (2009). Rationale for youth preparation and entrepreneurship education in the face of global economic crisis in Nigeria. *Annals of Modern Education*, 1(1), 224-232.
- [14]. Owusu - Ansah, W. A. (2004). *The impact of entrepreneurship education on career intentions and aspiration of tertiary students in Ghana*. A paper presented at the 49th World Conference of International Council for Small Business, 20th to 23rd June 2004, Johannesburg, South Africa.
- [15]. Postigo, S. & Tamborini, M. F. (2002). *Entrepreneurship education in Argentina: The case of San Andres University*. Paper Presented for Internationalizing Entrepreneurship Education and Training Conference (INTENT 2002), Malaysia, July 8 - 10.
- [16]. Ronstadt, R. (1985). The Educated entrepreneurs: A new era of entrepreneurial education is beginning. *American Journal of Small Business*. 10 , 7 - 23.
- [17]. Thandi, H. & Sharma, R. (2004). MBA students preparedness for entrepreneurial efforts. *Tertiary Education and Management*. (10), 209 - 226.
- [18]. Tkachev, A. & Kolvereid, L. (1999). Self employment intentions among Russian students. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, 11(3), 269-280.
- [19]. Scott, M. F. & Twomey, D. F (1988). The long term supply of entrepreneurs: students career aspirations in relation to entrepreneurship. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 26(4) 5 - 14.
- [20]. Sandholtz, K. (1990). MBA attitudes, *The College Edition of the National Business Employment Weekly*, spring.
- [21]. Varela, R. & Jimenez, J. E. (2001). *The effect of entrepreneurship education in the Universities of Cali*. Frontiers of entrepreneurship research, Babson Conference proceedings.
- [22]. Wilson, F., Kickul, J. & Marlino, D (2007). *Gender, entrepreneurial self-efficacy, and entrepreneurial career intentions: Implication of entrepreneurship education*, *Entrepreneurship: Theory and practice* 406.
- [23]. Weihe, H. J. & Reich, F. R. (1993). Entrepreneurial interest among business students: Results of an international Study. In H. A. Klant (Ed.) *Entrepreneurship and Business Development*.

Table 1: Career intention of tertiary education students after graduation

Career Intentions	Percentage (%)	N
Further Studies	15%	75
Self Employment	26.8%	134
Employment	29.6%	148
Further Studies and Part Time Business	7.6%	38
Employment and Part Time Business	21.6%	105
Total	100%	500

Table 2: Level of skills acquired to start a business

Responsive Frequency	Percentage (%)	N
High Skills	28.8%	144
Moderate Skills	47.2%	236
Low Skills	24%	120
Total	100%	500

Table 3: Population t-test of the benefit of Entrepreneurship Education (E.E)

Variable	n	x	μ	SD	t
Benefits of E.E	500	31.90	-	5.09	30.314*
Reference score	-	-	25.0	-	

*significant at .05, df = 499 critical t=1.65

Table 4: Population t-test of the perceived barriers to business start-up by students

Variable	n	x	μ	SD	t
Perceived Barriers	500	26.93	-	6.68	6.443*
Reference score	-	-	25.0	-	

*significant at .05, df = 499 critical t=1.